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**A STUDY ON RURAL INFRASTRUCTURE FUNDING
– A CASE STUDY ON PAVOOR GRAM PANCHAYAT****Mr Shakin Raj*, Mr Arjun Prakash****

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*Mail: shakinraj03@gmail.com**Mail: arjunetu@gmail.com**Abstract:**

In a country, infrastructure plays an important role in supporting nation's economic growth. Rural infrastructure assumes great importance in India because of the country's predominantly rural nature and the crucial linkages of rural infrastructure to economic growth, poverty alleviation and human development as a whole in the country. In fact, as per Census 2011, there are 6.4 lakh villages in India, which shelter more than two-third of the country's population. In such a scenario, the role and importance of rural infrastructure in India cannot be neglected. The study on operational and financial operations of the Pavoore Gram Panchayat helps to know the various sources of funds received and amount of funds actually utilized towards rural infrastructure development.

Keywords: infrastructure, rural infrastructure**1. INTRODUCTION**

In a country, infrastructure plays an important role in supporting nation's economic growth. Rural infrastructure assumes great importance in India because of the country's predominantly rural nature and the crucial linkages of rural infrastructure to economic growth, poverty alleviation and human development as a whole in the country. In fact, as per Census 2011, there are 6.4 lakh villages in India, which shelter more than two-third of the country's population. In such a scenario, the role and importance of rural infrastructure in India cannot be neglected. The study on operational and financial operations of the Pavoore Gram Panchayat helps to know the various sources of funds received and amount of funds actually utilized towards rural infrastructure development.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To study the grants sanctioned by the union and state government towards the development of Gram Panchayat infrastructure.
- To study the allocation of funds to Gram Panchayat through fourteenth finance of union budget.

3. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

PRIMARY DATA: The primary data was gathered from personal interviews with the Gram Panchayat employees and higher officials. The entire survey was conducted in Pavoore Gram Panchayat, which consisted of the information on understanding the different sources of funding received by the Gram Panchayat from government and other alternative sources. The

data was collected through interviews from the month of November 2018. Information was drawn from employees, higher officials and files maintained by the Gram Panchayat.

SECONDARY DATA The secondary data was collected from various sources like newspapers, articles, books and files maintained by the Gram Panchayat.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Soumya Manjunath & Elumalai Kannan (2017)

The present study analyzed the effect of rural infrastructure on agricultural development in the southern Indian state of Karnataka. The study used district-level data for 30 years period and employed infrastructure availability and utilization framework to examine the relationship between the rural infrastructure and agricultural development. The analysis showed that infrastructure availability and infrastructure utilization had positive and significant effect on agricultural productivity growth. The effect of infrastructure utilization on productivity growth seemed to be higher than that of infrastructure availability. Further, the combined effect of availability and utilization of infrastructure had larger effect on agricultural productivity. The analysis of spatial convergence of agricultural productivity growth showed that districts converge in land productivity over time.

Amar Kumar Mohanty & Narayan Chandra Nayak & Bani Chatterjee (2016)

In pursuit of achieving and maintaining high human development, infrastructure is said to play a critical role. The present paper examines the spatial differences in infrastructural facilities and human development across 30 districts of Odisha, and consequently, tries to find out the impact of infrastructure on human development in the state. The study records significant regional differences in the level of human development as well as infrastructural development in Odisha. It applies a data model to examine the effects of composite infrastructure and its individual components on human development and its three dimensions. The study establishes close linkage between infrastructure and human development. Telecommunication, postal services, village electricity, banking, school and drinking water facilities play significant roles in the process of attaining high level of human development. In order to achieve high and sustained human development, the state needs to prioritize its efforts towards infrastructure creation for these regions.

Ramakrishna Nallathiga (2015)

Infrastructure is vital for economic growth and development of any nation. Although national infrastructure plays an important role, the development of infrastructure and its growth, however, may depend upon the peculiar priorities and performance of state governments in a federal structure such as that of India. India has been growing extensively in the terms of infrastructure but the states may show differential performance in terms of infrastructure development due to various reasons. It is in this context that this article reports the findings from a study to assess the performance of Indian states on a constructible infrastructure using levels and growth data.

5. FINDINGS

1. There is a gradual decrease in the funds allocated by the government in the year 2014-15 and 2015-16 by 5.28% and 6.3%. The amount sanctioned in 2016-17 is almost 3 times and in 2017-18 is almost 5 times the amount sanctioned in the base year.
2. The funds raised by the issue of business license in 2014-15 is double the amount raised in the base year. There is almost 70-80% increase in the amount raised in 2015-16 and 2016-17

when compared with the base year. The increase in the funds raised is more in 2017-18 as compared to earlier years.

3. There is a considerable decrease in the funds raised by issue of building license when compared with 2013-14. The amount raised in 2014-15 and 2015-16 has decreased by 47.66% and 32.49% respectively. 54% of base year amount is raised in the last two years.

4. The amount raised through Panchayat building rent has continuously increased up to 2015-16 though in different proportions i.e. 42-51%. The amount raised in 2016-17 though greater than base year, has decreased by almost 21-22% than 2015-16. There is a further hike in the amount raised in 2017-18 by 54.19% than the base year.

5. The amount raised through house tax has continuously increased from 2013-14 to 2015-16, i.e. 100-162.42%. There is a downfall in the amount raised in 2016-17 and 2017-18 when compared to 2015-16 by 5.88% and 10.37%.

6. The amount raised through Library tax has continuously increased from 2013-14 to 2015-16, i.e. 100-162.41%. There is a downfall in the amount raised in 2016-17 and 2017-18 when compared to 2015-16 by 5.87% and 10.37%.

7. The amount raised through education tax has continuously increased up to 2015-16 though in different proportions i.e. 132-164%. There is a downfall in the amount raised in 2016-17 and 2017-18 when compared to 2015-16 by 5.87% and 10.37%.

8. There is a considerable increase in all the above years from 2013 to 2018. The percentage in 2014-15 is 107.79% as compared to 100 in 2013-14. The funds raised through issue of water connection bills increase at a pace of 25.31% in 2015-16, 42.46% in 2016-17 and 78.61% in 2017-18 over the base year 2013-14.

9. The amount sanctioned through MGNRE Act exhibits a continuous increasing trend over the period. The percentage in 2014-15 is 128.05% as compared to 100 in 2013-14. The increase in the funds raised is more in 2017-18 as compared to earlier years. The funds sanctioned through MGNRE Act increase at a pace of 167.87% in 2015-16, 310.85% in 2016-17 and 365.54% in 2017-18.

10. There is a decline in trend as there is no State allocations towards housing plans under Basava Vasathi Yojana for the year 2014-15 and 2015-16. A sharp increase of 53.49% is noticed in 2016-17 and there is a dip in 2018-19 to 9.19%.

11. There is a decline in trend as there is no State allocations towards housing plans under Ambedkar Vasathi Yojana for the year 2014-15. There is a sudden increase in trend to 164.8% in 2015-16 and again oscillating between 0 to 43.65% in 2016-17 and 2017-18. There is an overall decrease of 56.35% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

12. There is a decline in trend as there is no State allocations through Pradhan Mantri Awaaz Yojana for the year 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2016-17. A sharp increase of 31.25% is noticed in 2017-18. The chart shows overall decrease of 68.75% over the five year period.

13. There is a considerable decrease in the amount sanctioned for irrigation activities when compared with 2013-14. There is a drop in trend to 71.92% in 2014-15. A slight increase to 80.7% and 83.95% is noticed in the year 2015-16 and 2016-17. 24.69% of base year amount is raised in the last year.

14. The chart shows a slight decrease of 11.48% in 2014-15 in sanctioned towards maintenance and construction of Underground Drainages. A sign of improvement is seen in 2015-16 to 128.73% and sliding down to 32.17% in 2016-17. There is a rebound in trend with the increase to 125.79% in 2017-18. The chart shows a positive trend as there is 25.79% increase over the base year.

15. There is a considerable decrease to 2.88% in the funds sanctioned for construction and maintenance of roads in 2014-15 when compared with 2013-14. The amount sanctioned in 2015-16 and 2017-18 has decreased by 95.38% and 58.5% respectively. 94.04% of base year amount is raised in the last year.

16. The amount sanctioned for setting up street lights and maintenance of Community has increased in 2014-15 to 704.23%. There is a downfall in the amount sanctioned in 2015-16 as no amount is sanctioned for setting up street lights and maintenance of Community. There is a rebound in trend with the increase to 1408.45% in 2016-17 and to 2464.79% in 2017-18. The chart shows a positive trend as there is 2364.79% increase over the base year.

17. The closing balance of fund available with the Gram Panchayat has increased by 41.31% in 2014-15. A slight fall in trend is seen in 2015-16 by 62.93% when compared to 2014-15. There is a sudden increase in trend to 539.63% in 2016-17 and again oscillating to 515.78% in 2017-18. It shows a positive trend as there is an overall increase of 415.78% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

18. There is a considerable decrease of 8.02% in the treasury of the Gram Panchayat in 2014-15 when compared with 2013-14. There is a sudden increase in trend to 160.45% in 2015-16. A further rise to 217% in trend is seen in 2016-17. There is a drastic drop in trend from 217% to 90.21% in 2017-18. There is an overall decrease of 9.79% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

19. As 46.45% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of roads. As it forms the major part of the total amount sanctioned, it states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of roads in 2013-14.

The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on other activities such as setting up of street lights and maintenance of community halls as only 0.38% of total amount sanctioned is allotted towards this area in 2013-14.

20. As 57.62% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of underground drainages. As it forms the major part of the total amount sanctioned, it states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of underground drainages in 2014-15. The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on housing activities, and on construction and maintenance of roads as only 3.61% of total amount sanctioned is allotted towards this area in 2014-15.

21. As 48.56% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of underground drainages. It states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of underground drainages in 2015-16.

The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on other activities such as setting up of street lights and maintenance of community halls as no fund allotment is made towards this area in 2015-16.

22. The Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on housing activities in 2016-17. The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on other activities such as setting up of street lights and maintenance of community halls as only 5.5% of total amount sanctioned is allotted towards this area in 2016-17.

23. As 40.68% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of roads. It states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of roads in 2017-18.

24. The amount allotted towards payment of the employee's salary has increased from 100-165.77% in 2014-15. The amount raised in 2015-16 though greater than base year by 51.17%,

has decreased by almost 14.6% than 2015-16. There is a further hike in the amount paid in 2016-17 by 67.73% than the base year.

There is a further decline in trend in the year 2017-18 as the trend has dropped to 21.05%. From the information depicted in this chart it shows a negative trend as there is an overall decrease of 78.95% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

6. SUGGESTIONS

- To encourage local initiatives to fund existing infrastructure problems for small network development.
- Implementation of new technologies, which are cost effective even at low volumes. For example, a watershed can be developed only for one or two villages. Small hydel plants can be built to utilize the flow of small mountainous streams and generate power. These technologies can be used in remote and sparsely populated areas.
- Gram Panchayat should allow private providers to pool their funds in Roads and power projects by encouraging private providers by validating their claims, through incentives for limited ownership of the created assets, and by providing them with opportunities to recover costs through user fees.
- Gram Panchayat should invite proposals from various service providers as maximum fund is allocated to irrigation activity i.e. installation of water pump towards only one service provider.
- The online portal should be open to the public.
- Government should implement a rule compelling the Gram Panchayat to maintain accounting journals and ledgers.
- The educational qualification for the post of the President of the Gram Panchayat should be set by the government, as it indirectly affects the efficiency of the management.

7. CONCLUSION

The study of Rural Infrastructure Funding has focused mainly on the funds allotted by the Government to the Gram Panchayat and funds raised through various sources of funds. The underlying objective of the study was to assess the current status of rural infrastructure in the Pavor Village by focusing on the funding done towards the five sectors i.e. Roads, drainage system, drinking water supply, setting up of street lights along with maintaining of community buildings and sanitation. According to the study findings, the rural populations is not covered by basic infrastructure facilities like telecom, power, and roads .As far as drinking water is concerned, while most rural inhabitants have access to some sort of water source, the quality and maintenance of these sources leave a lot to be desired. The dismal state of rural infrastructure has hardly improved. This implies that five decades of development planning in India has been unable to ensure a decent living for a large number of people residing in rural areas. Despite many large-scale rural development schemes, the absolute number of people in poverty has not decline .

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